

ADVANTAGES OF PERMANENT MAGNET SYNCHRONOUS GENERATORS

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Today, no one will be surprised by the fact that many relays and sensors, rotors of motors and generators, even in such grandiose structures as industrial hydroelectric power plants and wind turbines, use neodymium magnets in their units instead of the excitation windings that are becoming a thing of the past. Large currents through the rotor windings are no longer needed here, and sparking brushes have long been dispensed with.

Brushless synchronous generators owe their durability to powerful neodymium magnets, as do multi-turn [brushless dc motors](#), whose rotors also have neodymium magnets on their poles. Such engines are easy to operate and do not require any special maintenance. By the way, it has long been known that the power [generator](#) directly depends on the strength of the magnets used on its rotor.

To overcome these problems, some wind turbine manufacturers are introducing [magnetic mounting solutions](#). These innovative systems use [strong neodymium magnets](#) strategically placed along the length of ladders and other equipment to securely attach them to the tower's steel walls. This approach eliminates the need for drilling or welding, maintaining the structural integrity of the tower and reducing construction time and costs.

Fig.1. Control system of a synchronous generator with permanent magnets

The class of wind generators in the present wind energy industry include squirrel-cage induction generator (SCIG), wound rotor induction generator (WRIG), doubly fed induction generator (DFIG), permanent magnet synchronous generator (PMSG), wound rotor synchronous generator (WRSG), and high-temperature-superconducting synchronous generator (HTS-SG). By combining the wind generators with power electronic converters, various configurations for wind energy conversion systems (WECS) have been researched and commercialized over the past 35

years. The following five WECS types are offered by many WT manufacturers to achieve fixed-speed, semivariable speed, and full-variable speed operations:

Type 1: Fixed-speed WECS with SCIG, soft starter, and reactive power compensator. The SCIG operates 1% above the synchronous speed.

Type 2: Semivariable speed WECS with WRIG, converter-controlled variable rotor resistor, soft starter, and reactive power compensator. The operating speed range for WRIG is 10% above the synchronous speed.

Type 3: Semivariable speed WECS with DFIG and partial power converter in rotor circuit. The DFIG speed can be varied within 30% above and below the synchronous speed.

Type 4: Full-variable speed WECS with wind generator (SCIG, PMSG, WRSG, or HTS-SG) and full power converter in stator circuit. The wind generator speed can be varied from 0% to 100%.

Type 5: Full-variable speed WECS with WRSG, torque converter, and field exciter in rotor circuit. The operating speed range of WECS is from 0% to 100%.

Neodymium magnets are a real find for many areas, and their use is only expanding. Their strength and compactness allow them to be used where conventional magnets would be useless. Synchronous generators with permanent magnets in wind turbines are characterized by high efficiency, reliability and compact design. Their use in energy is not only economically advantageous, but also an environmentally acceptable solution. The use of wind turbines is one of the promising solutions for the development of wind energy in Uzbekistan.